

OrganKits project

OrganKits partners have been working on the project and have several updates to share! The main results of OrganKits are presented in this 3rd newsletter. Want to find more? Contact us or visit our website

Top stories

OrganKits: on its way to becoming an example of good practice

Having passed the halfway point of its implementation, the OrganKits project underwent the mid-term evaluation by the experts of the Spanish Service...

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Advancing Anatomical Science: Specialized Plastination Training at Discover-IN

Plastination, an innovative anatomical technique, has revolutionized the way we preserve and study biological tissues.

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OrganKits: Educational innovation in European secondary school classrooms

On May 21-22, the team of the Erasmus+ project "OrganKits: a new material for STEAM education based on plastination" met in Portugal to discuss the results of the first implementation phase.

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OrganKits at the 7th OPEN SPACE of the European University Foundation (EUF)

The 7th edition of the "Open Space" organized by the European University Foundation was hosted by the University of Murcia from May 28 to 31, 2024.

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